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The Open Energy Knowledge Graph (OEKG) For Interoperable Energy Scenarios

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Agenda

- Challenges in describing energy scenarios

- Open Energy Ontology

OEO

- As backbone for conceptualization

- Open Energy Knowledge Graph

OEKG

- As representation of factual information

- Open Energy Platform

OEP

- As application

Open Energy Family

Challenges for the description and comparison of energy scenarios

- Scenarios may **vary broadly**, depending on research question, storyline, level of detail/complexity, modelling approach,...
- **Different type of data**: input data, narratives, study report, output projection data, metadata...
- Scenarios are **published** in a **variety of ways**
- Not all data is published, and published data often fails to meet **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
- **Manual comparison** is cumbersome

Quelle: Dieckhoff et al.: *Zur Interpretation von Energieszenarien* (Schriftenreihe Energiesysteme der Zukunft), München 2014.

Scenario bundles

*A **scenario bundle** contains all the relevant information to understand a scenario's context and makes it easier to potentially reuse quantitative data for your own.*

- Created to collect and **describe** energy scenarios systematically
- Not restricted to a specific data model
- Bundling (=collecting and connecting) all relevant information
 - Study information
 - Scenario description (scenario type, regions, years, sectors, technologies, ...)
 - Model and framework information
 - Publication details
 - Input and output data sets, incl. Metadata
 - FAIR, openly licenced

Solution to challenge

To enable interoperability among different energy scenarios,
we need a **harmonized terminology**.

Open Energy Ontology

Categorization/Conceptualization

- Taxonomy
- Non-hierarchical Relations
- Unambiguous definitions
- Modular structures
- Re-use other ontologies

Solar power technology is a kind of Power generation technology, which in turn is a kind of Energy technology

Ontology + Knowledge Graph

Categorization/Conceptualization

Instantiation/Factual information

A specific scenario bundle with the name **Example Bundle** contains the **Solar power technology** as one of its considered technologies.

Open Energy Knowledge Graph schema

Open Energy Knowledge Graph schema

Open Energy Ontology hierarchy

Ontology Terms
 RDFS Labels
 Literals
 Knowledge Graph Entities

Open Energy Knowledge Graph (example)

- Institutions

Open Energy Knowledge Graph (example)

- Institutions
- Funding sources

Open Energy Knowledge Graph (example)

- Institutions
- Funding sources
- Descriptors

■ Ontology Terms

■ Knowledge Graph Entities

Open Energy Knowledge Graph (example)

- Institutions
- Funding sources
- Descriptors
- Scenarios
 - Scenario years
 - Regions
 - Scenario descriptors
 - Input data
 - Output data
- ...

OEKG

Open Energy Knowledge Graph interoperability (example)

If **different** scenario bundles in the OEKG **share** an entity, they have a common factor that makes them similar in this particular aspect.

Two different scenario bundles from two institutes cover **Solar power technology**.

Working with the Open Energy Knowledge Graph

Scenario bundles: page on the Open Energy Platform (OEP)

The screenshot shows the Open Energy Platform (OEP) website. The navigation bar at the top includes links for Database, Scenario Bundles, Ontology, Academy, and About. The main heading is 'Open Energy Platform' with the tagline 'Make your energy system modelling process transparent!'. Below this, there are four main cards: Database, Scenario Bundles (highlighted with a green circle), Ontology, and Academy. Each card contains an icon, a title, a short description, and a 'Learn more' button. At the bottom, there are three additional sections: API, Open Science, and Open Energy Community, each with an icon, a short description, and a 'Learn more' button. The footer contains links for Contact, Privacy Policy, and Terms of Use.

Database Scenario Bundles Ontology Academy About

Adel Logout

Open Energy Platform

Make your energy system modelling process transparent!

Database

Are you interested in data? Visualize the database to explore it. All contributors publish datasets under an open license, so you can securely download and work with it. Are you interested in sharing your own data? This is the place to upload it.

[Database](#)

Scenario Bundles

Do you want to learn more about scenarios, the models used to project them and the actual data? Then, this is the right place for you. If you contributed data to the OEP this is the place where you can provide more context by creating your own scenario bundle.

[Scenario Bundles](#)

Ontology

Ontology refers to a collection of domain specific terminology and their relationships. Come here to learn more about the Open Energy Ontology (OEO), which helps with data annotation and management.

[Ontology](#)

Academy

The Open Energy Academy (OEA) provides courses as well as dedicated tutorials covering important topics around the Open Energy Family (OEF) tools and the Open Energy Platform (OEP). You will also find short answers to urgent questions.

[Academy](#)

API

Learn how to download and publish open data on the OEP using the API.

[Learn more](#)

Open Science

Good scientific practice needs open licenses for software, data and content.

[Learn more](#)

Open Energy Community

Collaborate and contribute to the development on GitHub.

[Learn more](#)

Contact Privacy Policy Terms of Use

Scenario bundles (View)

Each row in the list is a **Scenario Bundle**

Filter Reset Compare scenarios LIST CARDS + Create New

Study name ↑	Acronym	Scenarios	Date of publication
Klimaschutzszenario 2050 - 2. Modellierungsrunde	DE-KSz-2050-R2	AMS (2012) KS 80 KS 95	2015-12-18
Dekarbonisierung Verkehr - Rückkopplung Energiesystem	DeV-KopSys		
Untersuchungen zur Energiestrategie Brandenburgs	appBBB_gruene2030	appBBB_ES2030 appBBB_gruene2030 appBBB_kohlefrei_gruene2030	2017-03-06
Consolidated and Harmonised GHG Emission Projections from European Legislation	EU-CH-GHG	WEM WAM WOM	2022-11-28
Rahmendaten für den Projektionsbericht 2023	DE-R-PB-2023	WEM WAM	2022-12-15
GHG emission projection data submitted in 2019 by Germany under Regulation (EU) 525/2013	DE-MMR-2019	WEM	2019-05-15
PROJECT SEDOS - Die Bedeutung der Sektorintegration im Rahmen der Energiewende in Deutschland – Modellierung mit einem nationalen Open Source ReferenzEnergieSystem	SEDOS	Scenario frame	2023/1/1

Scenario bundles (View)

Entities in the knowledge graph have specific types from the ontology
greenhouse gas emission is a class in the OEO

https://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/o eo/OEO_00000199

Ontology

Overview / Open Energy Ontology / Class - greenhouse gas emission

Label: greenhouse gas emission

Definition:

A greenhouse gas emission is an emission that releases a greenhouse gas.

← View Edit
Share Delete

Klimaschutzszenario 2050 - 2. Modellierungsrunde

Acronym DE-KSz-2050-R2

Contact person(s) · Hannah Förster · Lukas Emele ·

Institutions Öko-Institut e.V. · Fraunhofer ISI ·

Funding sources Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz, Bau und Reaktorsicherheit ·

Descriptors sufficient peak e Greenhouse gas emissions total net electricity generation degree of electrification

Abstract Three scenarios were created for the time frame up to 2050. The framework of targets for Germany, which its 2010/2011 Energy Concept put on the energy and climate policy agenda forms the core and basis of the development and analyses of the scenarios in this report. With its Energy Concept and its accelerated phase-out of nuclear energy, a comprehensive set of energy and climate policy targets for the short, medium and long term has been established for Germany. Key questions of this research project were: What emission reduction could be achieved if Germany's current energy and climate policy is continued? What policies and strategies are necessary to achieve the climate protection targets? What cost-benefit relationships thereby arise for consumers and the economy? Since the energy economic and political environment is very dynamic at the moment, these scenarios should be updated yearly for a period of three years. The results of the second round of modelling provided, inter alia, the scientific basis for the development of Germany's Climate Action Plan 2050

Scenarios (3)
Publications
Sectors and technology
Models and frameworks

Name Aktuelle-Maßnahmen-Szenario (2012)

Scenario bundles (Create)

A scenario bundle contains:

- Funding sources
- Authors
- Models
- Frameworks
- Sectors
- Scenarios
- Scenario years
- Regions
- Interacting regions
- ...

The screenshot shows a web interface for creating a scenario bundle. It features a top navigation bar with tabs for 'Basic information', 'Study detail', 'Publications', 'Sectors and technology', 'Scenarios', and 'Metadata'. The 'Sectors and technology' tab is active, displaying a list of sector divisions and sectors. A tooltip is visible over the 'CRF sector (IPCC 2006): integrated circuit or semiconductor' entry, providing a detailed description of this sector. On the right side, there are sections for 'Spatial regions' and 'Scenario years'. A dropdown menu is open, showing a list of regions with 'Germany' selected. The interface includes a 'Save' button in the top right corner and a 'View/Edit' button in the top left corner.

Scenario bundles (Create)

A scenario bundle contains:

- Funding sources
- Authors
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- Regions
- Interacting regions
- ...

Tooltips show
the definitions
of concepts in
ontologies

Spatial regions ⓘ

A study region is a spatial region that is under investigation and consists entirely of one or more subregions.
More info from Open Energy Ontology (OEO)...

Scenario years ⓘ

Sector divisions ⓘ

Sectors ⓘ

KSG sector division

CRF sectors (IPCC 2006)

NC/BR sector division

Others

CRF sector (IPCC 2006): other transportation

CRF sector (IPCC 2006): solid waste disposal

CRF sector (IPCC 2006): refrigeration and air conditioning

CRF sector (IPCC 2006): integrated circuit or semiconductor

The CRF sector (IPCC 2006) integrated circuit or semiconductor is an industry sector defined by the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories: Emissions of CF4, C2F6, C3F8, i-C4F8, C4F10, CSF6, CHF3, CHF2F, NF3 and SF6 from uses of these gases in Integrated Circuit (IC) manufacturing in rapidly evolving ways and in varying amounts, which depend on product (e.g., memory or logic devices) and equipment manufacturer.
More info from Open Energy Ontology (OEO)...

French Guiana

French Polynesia

French Southern Territories (the)

Gabon

Gambia (the)

Georgia

Germany

Dropdowns retrieve
concepts from
ontologies

Scenario bundles (Comparison - Selection step)

Selecting scenarios from different bundles

Untersuchungen zur Energiestrategie Brandenburgs	appBBB_gruene2030	<input type="radio"/> appBBB_ES2030 <input type="radio"/> appBBB_gruene2030 <input type="radio"/> appBBB_kohlefrei_gruene2030
Consolidated and Harmonised GHG Emission Projections from European Legislation	EU-CH-GHG	<input type="radio"/> WEM <input type="radio"/> WAM <input type="radio"/> WOM
Rahmendaten für den Projektionsbericht 2023	DE-R-PB-2023	<input checked="" type="radio"/> WEM <input checked="" type="radio"/> WAM
GHG emission projection data submitted in 2019 by Germany under Regulation (EU) 525/2013	DE-MMR-2019	<input checked="" type="radio"/> WEM

Scenario bundles (Comparison - Results)

Database Scenario Bundles Ontology Academy About Adel Logout

Scenario Bundles
COMPARISON

Selecting aspects for comparisons

Criteria
 Specific dataset Study name Study dataset Descriptors Regions Interregional regions Scenario years Input datasets Output datasets

Base scenario

WEM
WEM
Base scenario

Study name:
Rahmendaten für den Projektionsbericht 2023

Descriptors:

Scenario years:

Output datasets:

WAM

Study name:
Rahmendaten für den Projektionsbericht 2023

Descriptors:

Scenario years:

Output datasets:

WEM

Study name:
Emission scenario data submitted in 2019 by Germany under Regulation (EU) 525/2013

Descriptors:

Scenario years:

Output datasets:

■ Similarity

■ Dissimilarity

Scenario bundles (Documentation)

Semantic structure

The screenshot shows the 'Open Energy Knowledge Graph' website. On the left, there is a navigation menu with categories like 'Family Members', 'Knowledge Representation', 'Software Architecture', 'Specification and Templates', and 'Open Process Integration'. The main content area displays a complex ontology diagram with nodes and relationships, including terms like 'CO2 emissions Descriptor', 'Example_Scenario', 'CRF sectors (IPCC 2006)', and 'Energy technology'. Below the main diagram is a tree view titled 'Open Energy Ontology hierarchy' showing a structured list of energy technologies such as 'Power generation technology', 'Fuel power technology', 'Coal power technology', 'Geothermal power technology', and 'Wind power technology'.

https://openenergyplatform.github.io/organisation/family_members/knowledge-representation/oe/kg/#structure

Developers' guide

The screenshot shows the 'Open Energy Platform Documentation' website. The left sidebar contains a navigation menu with sections like 'Installation & Code Documentation', 'Installation', 'Development setup', 'Architecture', 'Web-APIs', 'OEKG REST-API', 'OEKG API', and 'Features'. The main content area is titled 'Index' and includes a 'Django view for the scenario bundles' section with a 'Note' box. Below this, there is a 'Create a new bundle in OEKG' section with a URL and an 'An example of input parameters' section containing a JSON code block.

```

{
  "id": "new",
  "uid": "6157d6de-7a7b-a61e-21d3-a8f936b19056",
  "study_name": "Example study name",
  "acronym": "Example acronym",
  "abstract": "Example abstract ...",
  "institution": [
    {
      "iri": "7f88ad9dc-7f8b-6c65-6a5f-8fc54fe8221b",
      "name": "Oeko-Institut e.V."
    },
    {
      "iri": "8e1515b9-9b1f-fa06-a3a2-d552b8ea7dcd",
      "name": "Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg"
    }
  ],
  "funding_source": [
    {
      "iri": "82dd628d-f748-568b-b8cd-86466cf90f1a",
      "name": "Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und nukleare Sicherheit"
    }
  ]
}

```

<https://openenergyplatform.github.io/oeplatform/install-and-documentation/oeplatform-code/web-api/oe/kg-api/>

Conclusion

- Different scenario bundles based on a common terminology

The screenshot displays a web interface for a dataset titled "Consolidated and Harmonised GHG Emission Projections from European Legislation". The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options like "Name", "Acronym", "Abstract", "Description", and "Years". The main content area shows the following details:

- Acronym:** CHSHG
- Contact person(s):** Hannah Förster - Christian Winger -
- Institutions:** Öko-Institut e.V. -
- Funding sources:** Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz -
- Descriptors:** Greenhouse gas emissions - CO2 emissions -
- Abstract:** We compiled data and harmonised their notation for GHG emission projection data that European Member States submit under European Legislation mandatorily every two years (and voluntarily in between). The series of tables starts from the GHG emission projections submitted by European Member States in 2014 and is amended as new data becomes available in the reporting platform. (These datasets have the suffix _aio or _rep). The purpose of providing these compilations is to enable straight forward data comparison across the whole series of submissions. We also harmonised data notation across all available submission years for the same datasets but quality checked and approved and compiled by the European Environment Agency (EEA). For these datasets we harmonised data notation across the whole series (These datasets have the suffix _aei).

Below the text is a table with the following structure:

	Scenarios (3)	Publications	Sectors and technology	Models and frameworks
Name	With existing measures scenario			
Acronym	WEM			
Abstract	A with existing measures scenario (WEM) is a policy scenario that includes policy instruments and transformative measures that have been adopted and implemented. The WEM scenario is a mandatory reporting requirement for European Member States, according to European legislation (the latest being the EU Governance Regulation). The datasets provided on the OEP include all European Member States at the submission year. For example, data for the United Kingdom is not available in any datasets submitted after Brexit. For ease, the countries below include all current and former EU Member States. The datasets (suffix _aei) provided includes the WEM scenario data only for those Member States who provided that data.			
Descriptors	with existing measures scenario - emission scenario - greenhouse gas emission scenario - policy scenario - CO2 emission scenario -			
Years	2030 - 2020 - 2040 - 2050 - 2025 - 2035 - 2045 -			

Conclusion

- Different scenario bundles based on a common terminology

The Open Energy Knowledge Graph

Conclusion

- Different scenario bundles based on a common terminology

The Open Energy Knowledge Graph

Bundle 1

Bundle 2

Conclusion

- Different scenario bundles based on a common terminology

The Open Energy Knowledge Graph

Bundle 1

Bundle 2

Conclusion

- Different scenario bundles based on a common terminology

The Open Energy Knowledge Graph

Bundle 1

Bundle 3

Bundle 2

Conclusion

- Different scenario bundles based on a common terminology

The Open Energy Knowledge Graph

Bundle 1

Shared parts

Bundle 3

Conclusion

- Scenario bundles are unified in the **Open Energy Knowledge Graph**.

Scenario bundles are parts of a single underlying knowledge graph

Limitations

- Ontology coverage is still evolving
- Currently a simple form of comparison is enabled.
 - Comparing energy scenarios based on ontological similarity is difficult due to technological, regional, and political complexities.
- Data tables are structured in different ways.
 - A normalization step is needed before integrating information about datasets into the OEKG.
- So far, only small amount of annotations with respect to the ontology.
 - Limited number of scenario bundles are uploaded.

Future work

- An **Ontology-Based Data Integration (OBDI)** system that enables users to **quantitatively** compare various energy and climate scenarios.

The data tab

id	country_code	category	year	gas	scenario	unit	ry	subtable	notation	value
1	AT	1 Energy	2018	CH4	WAM	kt	false	A		22.961961306141
2	AT	1 Energy	2018	CO2	WAM	kt	false	A		53375.32676190
3	AT	1 Energy	2018	N2O	WAM	kt	false	A		2.156241154009
4	AT	1 Energy	2018	Total ESR GHGs	WAM	kt CO2e	false	A		38956.67538794
5	AT	1 Energy	2018	Total ETS GHGs	WAM	kt CO2e	false	A		15589.38033475
6	AT	1 Energy	2018	Total GHGs	WAM	kt CO2e	false	A		54591.93565845
7	AT	1 Energy	2019	CH4	WAM	kt	true	A		22.32385480555
8	AT	1 Energy	2019	CO2	WAM	kt	true	A		53840.317810891
9	AT	1 Energy	2019	N2O	WAM	kt	true	A		2.1797345913152
10	AT	1 Energy	2019	Total ESR GHGs	WAM	kt CO2e	true	A		39192.43961656

The Meta information tab


```

gas
  • Name: gas
  • Type: varchar(64)
  • Units: null
  • IsAbout: greenhouse gas
  • Name: greenhouse gas
  • Path: http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeso/OEO_00000020
  • Description: the greenhouse gas that is reported
  • ValueReference: methane
    • Name: methane
    • Path: http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeso/OEO_00000025
    • Value: 0:14
  carbon dioxide
    • Name: carbon dioxide
    • Path: http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeso/OEO_00000008
    • Value: CO2
  nitrous oxide
    • Name: nitrous oxide
    • Path: http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeso/OEO_00000027
    • Value: N2O
  nitrogen trifluoride
    • Name: nitrogen trifluoride
    • Path: http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeso/OEO_00000026
    • Value: NF3
  hydrofluorocarbon
    • Name: hydrofluorocarbon
    • Path: http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeso/OEO_00000219
    • Value: HFC
  perfluorocarbon
  
```

Data annotation
based on the
Open Energy
Ontology

Future work

- The data in a Virtual Knowledge Graph is not materialised, but rather virtualized.
 - Achieved through
 - **query rewriting.**
 - **semantic mappings**
 - Integrating data without moving and transforming them.

Virtual Knowledge Graph Ontology-Based Data access

Future work

- Establish more **complex relations** between the concepts in the **Open Energy Ontology** and reflect these connections in the Open Energy Knowledge Graph.
- Enhance the OEKG with **additional factual information**
- Introduce new features to the Open Energy Platform
 - A comprehensive **history of changes**
- Cultivate strong and effective connections with other well-established knowledge graphs, such as the **Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)** [1, 2].
 - **AI-based methods** for generating suggestions for extending the KG

[1] Markus Stocker, Allard Oelen, Mohamad Yaser Jaradeh, Muhammad Haris, Omar Arab Oghli, Golsa Heidari, Hassan Hussein, Anna-Lena Lorenz, Salomon Kabenamualu, Kheir Eddine Farfar, Manuel Prinz, Oliver Karras, Jennifer D'Souza, Lars Vogt, and Sören Auer (2023). FAIR scientific information with the Open Research Knowledge Graph. In B. Magagna (Ed.), *FAIR Connect*, vol. 1, issue 1, pp. 19–21. IOS Press. <https://doi.org/10.3233/fc-221513>

[2] Sören Auer, Allard Oelen, Muhammad Haris, Markus Stocker, Jennifer D'Souza, Kheir Eddine Farfar, Lars Vogt, Manuel Prinz, Vitalis Wiens, and Mohamad Yaser Jaradeh (2020). Improving Access to Scientific Literature with Knowledge Graphs. *Bibliothek Forschung und Praxis*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 516-529 <https://doi.org/10.1515/bfp-2020-2042>

**Open Energy
Ontology**
Conceptualization

**Open Energy
Knowledge Graph**
Factual information

**Open Energy
Database**
Quantitative data

Source code:

<https://github.com/OpenEnergyPlatform/oeplatform>

Website:

<https://openenergy-platform.org/scenario-bundles/main>

